

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: EMRICH****FIRST NAME: LINA****PROGRAM CODE: MMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).
The author did use Zotero to insert references.
The author did use Grammarly Premium.
The author used the following software: MSWord for Mac 2011 on macOS Mojave.

AN INTRODUCTION TO STUDYING AT EUCLID

1) INTRODUCTION

The first course at EUCLID is on International Academic and Professional Paper Writing. The first period of this course serves as an excellent way for new students to not only become familiar with the writing standard expected at EUCLID but also with the structure of upcoming courses. The 83-page document provided by EUCLID covers a range of subjects, including essay writing basics, the purpose of style, and the importance of avoiding plagiarism. The minimum standard for writing expected of EUCLID students will, no doubt, assist them on their path to writing competently for an international academic audience.

2) A MUCH-NEEDED REFRESHER

a) Essay Writing Basics

The last time I wrote academically was four years ago. I completed a bachelor's degree, which involved writing approximately eight pieces of coursework in three years. That was embarrassingly little writing. Therefore, the first part of the learning material on "Essay Writing The Basics" has been a much-needed refresher for me.

Writing academic papers can quickly become overwhelming, but the material boiled the process down to manageable steps while carving out the absolute essentials of good essay writing. My biggest takeaway from this part is always to identify the question that needs answering *first* so that the reading and note-taking which follow are intentional

and specific (EUCLID 2015, 3). After all, a good essay has to persuade its readers using substantial and sound evidence (EUCLID 2015, 2).

b) Common Mistakes to Avoid

The material also covered common mistakes in writing, clearing up any confusion students may have had regarding the nuances of the English language (EUCLID 2015, 47-51). It turns out that I was guilty of committing a few of these mistakes myself. When it comes to indicating possession through apostrophes, I always assumed that for words ending with an *s* the apostrophe always comes at the end. Therefore, it was surprising to learn that the apostrophe's positioning depends on whether the possessive noun is singular or plural (EUCLID 2015, 47).

I also used *that* and *which* interchangeably, instead of thinking about whether the phrase it precedes is restrictive or nonrestrictive (EUCLID 2015, 48). The biggest revelation, however, was learning about the rule governing when to use *I* and *me* (EUCLID 2015, 50-51). Despite the rule being exceedingly simple, I had always left that decision to my gut. In that sense, the learning material has been beneficial in addressing common questions all writers have but might be too ashamed to ask.

3) THE STANDARD AT EUCLID

A large portion of the learning material covers the importance of a style guide and how to avoid plagiarism. The two topics are closely related since correct citation practices, which adhere to a style guide, effectively prevent plagiarism. EUCLID has made it clear that students are expected to always follow a style guide and that plagiarism is a severe offense (EUCLID 2015, 12).

a) Committing to a Style

Style guides are essential for publications that gather and present the works of different authors. Without a clear structure to follow or fall back on, writing can appear chaotic. The main goal of having a style guide, therefore, is to ensure consistency throughout a publication (EUCLID 2015, 52).

EUCLID aims to prepare its students for professional academic writing by recommending the Chicago (or Turabian) Style (EUCLID 2015, 52). The learning material includes a twelve-page section named the “CMS Crib Sheet,” a distillation of the Chicago Style (EUCLID 2015, 66). Basic rules, such as those governing the use of abbreviations, capitalization, and italics, are covered under the heading “Chicago Style and Usage” (EUCLID 2015, 66-71). Whereas the section “Chicago Page Formats” reviews the exact formatting required for structuring a page (EUCLID 2015, 71-74). To guarantee correct formatting, students are asked to always start their assignments from the EUCLID template (EUCLID 2015, 6).

b) Avoiding Plagiarism

EUCLID (2015, 9) defines plagiarism as “using a source without giving credit.” Plagiarism is taken very seriously in the academic realm, so it is only natural that students are held to the same professional standard. The “CMS Crib Sheet” has a comprehensive section on endnotes, footnotes, and bibliographies, to ensure that credit is correctly given to where it is due (EUCLID 2015, 75-77). To make the citation process more manageable, students should also remember to include the exact source when taking notes (EUCLID 2015, 3).

4) UK VS. US ENGLISH

Despite my three-year experience writing academic papers in the United Kingdom, I have decided to make the switch to US English. Apart from the fact that EUCLID recommends the use of US English, it is also the more-used variation in education, publishing, and media (EUCLID 2015, 52-54). The section on “American vs. British English” has helped point out the crucial differences between UK and US English, especially in regards to honorifics, pluralized adjectives, and spelling (EUCLID 2015, 54-59). Nonetheless, the use of a spellcheck tool such as Grammarly will be vital.

5) RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE MATERIAL

Two parts within the reading material were more confusing than clarifying to me. First, the proper name format for EUCLID assignments, as shown in the content, did not include a program code (EUCLID 2015, 7). While the sample assignments and checklist given separately did include the program code. Second, the document emphasizes that US English always puts punctuation within quotation marks (EUCLID 2015, 48). However, multiple in-text citations place the period outside the quotation marks when followed by a parenthetical citation (EUCLID 2015, 16-19). It would be helpful if these disparities were clarified.

6) CONCLUSION

Period one of ACA-401 has been a tremendous help in setting me on track for completing the master's degree. I received a comprehensive introduction to the Chicago Style and the importance of avoiding plagiarism. This period also presented easy-to-follow guiding principles for writing an excellent academic essay. The introductory course is structured in the same way as upcoming classes, naturally easing students into their online degree at EUCLID. The remaining periods of this course will undoubtedly prepare me further for the learning structure at EUCLID and writing academic papers on a professional level.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. "ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1." Accessed September 11, 2019. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.